

AM4BAT PROJECT

Deliverable 6.3

Report on post-mortem and safety evaluation

- Grant agreement No. 101069756
- Topic: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-03
- Start date of the project: 01-07-2022
- Duration – 48 months

WP	6	Post-mortem and safety evaluation	
Dissemination level	PU	Due delivery date	30/11/2025
Nature	R	Actual delivery date	12/12/2025
Lead beneficiary	CEA		
Contributing beneficiaries			

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³ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final.

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Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue	Author
12-12-25	1	First Draft	BOUVET Justin (CEA) TARNOPOLSKIY Vasily (CEA) LAI Thanh-Loan (CEA)

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EIS: electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
SSB: Solid state batteries
SPE: Solid polymer electrolyte
HSPE: Hybrid Solid polymer electrolyte
FTIR: Fourier Transform InfraRed spectroscopy
ATR: Attenuated Total Reflectance

Executive summary

This report presents the outcomes of characterization activities conducted as part of the AM4BAT project to understand the degradation mechanism, dendrite formation and safety of the system developed. The work focuses on the characterization of the solid electrolytes' conductivities and interfaces with surrounding electrodes at beginning of life, the evolution of these characteristics during ageing in resting and cycling condition and finally the post-mortem observation of the cells.

In the first section, different solid electrolytes are used to characterize their bulk characteristics such as conductivity and transference number. The solid electrolyte interface with lithium metal was also evaluated. The results highlight the effect of the water contamination on the electrolyte performances. SAXS/WAXS analyses were also performed to study the temperature dependent structural properties of the HSE film and demonstrated the thermal stability of the material.

A second part investigates the post-mortem processes to analyse the different interfaces of the cells. A focus was made on cryo-fracture process allowing the acquisition of clean cross sections of the entire cell's stack.

Together, these results provide data to support tasks 6.1 and 6.2 activities and also helped the evaluation of battery components within the AM4BAT framework.

Introduction

The AM4BAT project aims to advance the development of next-generation lithium battery systems through the integration of novel materials. Deliverable 6.3 focuses on the characterization of the different components and interfaces found within solid and hybrid polymer electrolytes. This report presents an overview of the characterization as well as post-mortem activities helpful to better understand key processes influencing the performance of solid-state batteries.

The study is structured around two main tasks. First, different solid electrolytes are used to characterize their bulk characteristics at different stages of their life. The interface between solid electrolytes and lithium metal was also investigated. Then, a cryo-fracture protocol was developed to allow the observation of the cell's stack for post-mortem analyses.

Through these efforts, the report contributes to better understand the different components and interfaces to support the development of advanced battery components within the WP3,4, and 5 of the AM4BAT project.

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1. Component characterization

This section presents the components upon which the characterizations are performed, the details of the testing protocols and the associated results.

1.1. Studies components

For T6.3 activities, the characterized materials are the solid electrolyte (SE) and the anodeless current collectors.

2 batches of solid electrodes were sent by LEITAT after being developed in WP3. These two batches were received at different times of the project.

For SE, the first batch of material (batch 1) was composed of 3 different SE with the same polymer base but containing different amounts of LLZO. Table 1 presents the name used for the different SE and their composition.

Table 1: Details about the solid electrolytes sent by LEITAT in the second batch of material.

Name	Composition
SPE	AN:GN:TMPA (80% _w) : LiTFSI (20% _w) No LLZO
HSPE20	AN:GN:TMPA (80% _w) : LiTFSI (20% _w) + 20% _w LLZO
HSPE32	AN:GN:TMPA (80% _w) : LiTFSI (20% _w) + 31,9% _w LLZO

Before handling the SE, pictures were taken as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Pictures of the different SE from the first batch of material sent by LEITAT

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On Figure 1, it is possible to observe a yellow coloration for the different SE received. Also, the more LLZO in the SE, the more brittle the SE. For HSPE32, it was quite difficult to properly cut SE pellets.

Moreover, on the paper on which the SE is stored, a yellow coloration is visible (Figure 2 (a)). This could be due to absorption of the liquid components of the SE into the paper (slightly visible around HSPE20). 50 μ m thick lithium on copper (from CEA's stock) was used as a source of Li for the electrochemical tests. This lithium material was stored in the same pouch than the electrolyte. After storage, a white coloration was observed on the lithium metal (Figure 2 (b)) which gave clues to the non-stability of the lithium when in contact to the volatile species present in the SE.

Figure 2: (a) Coloration observed on SE (batch 1) storing paper and (b) picture of the lithium metal stored in the same pouch as the SE (batch 1).

Later in the project, LEITAT send a second batch of SE (batch 2) produced after improving their manufacturing protocol resulting in a lower water content in the SE thus increasing SE stability (see D3.4).

In this second batch 1 SE with LLZO and 1 without LLZO were received.

Table 2: Details about the solid electrolytes sent by LEITAT in the second batch of material.

Name	Composition
PSE	AN:GN:TMPA (80% _w) : LiTFSI (20% _w) + No LLZO
HSE20	AN:GN:TMPA (80% _w) : LiTFSI (20% _w) + 20% _w LLZO

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Figure 3 presents the HSE20 from batch 2. A strong coloration is observed on the material. After discussing with LEITAT, this coloration is a sign of SE ageing. Thus, the formulation with LLZO should not be considered.

Figure 3: Picture of the HSE with 20%_w LLZO from the second batch of material sent by LEITAT.

1.2. Experimental protocols

This section presents the experimental protocols for conductivity measurements, thermal stability tests and cycling tests. The tests are performed on coin-cells with the various configurations presented Figure 4.

Figure 4: Coin-cells configurations (a) with stainless steel electrodes and (b) lithium and/or anode-less current collector.

1.2.1. Electrolyte conductivity measurement and interface characterization protocols:

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For measuring electrolyte conductivity, symmetrical cells with the SE to study placed in between 2 stainless steel discs are assembled (see Figure 4) and they are tested from 60°C to -10°C using the following protocol:

1. Rest 2 h
2. PEIS, 10mV amplitude from 1MHz to 10mHz with 8 points per decade (5 periods)
3. Rest until 3 h passed from the start of step 2
4. Go to step 2 and change the temperature

The tested temperatures are: 20°C; 60°C; 40°C; 20°C; 0°C; -10°C; 0°C; 20°C; 40°C; 60°C; 20°C. Some temperatures are tested more than once for reproducibility purposes and to verify that some other temperatures don't deteriorate the SE.

The above protocol is also used to study both the interfaces and the SE ionic conductivity using cells with other configurations:

- Li/SE/Li
- Li/SE/anode-less
- Anode-less/SE/anode-less

These configurations from Figure 4 help study the interfaces between the SE and lithium metal and between the SE and the anode-less current collector.

1.2.2. Thermal stability evaluation protocols:

Thermal stability for the SE itself and the interfaces between the SE and either lithium metal or anode-less current collector was evaluated using the different cell formats presented earlier, but with the following protocol at the desired temperature:

1. Rest 30 min
2. PEIS, 10mV amplitude from 1MHz to 10mHz with 12 points per decade (3 periods)
3. Rest until 1 h passed from the start of step 2
4. Go to step 2

With this protocol, the interfaces and the SE bulk stabilities are evaluated every 2 hours.

1.2.3. Cycling evaluation protocol:

For the study of dendrite growth and interface evolution during cycling, only Li/SE/Li and Li/SE/anode-less can be used because they are the only two designs that allow Li ions to be exchanged. The following protocol was designed to study what is the critical C-rate before potential short circuits appear:

1. Rest 1 h
2. PEIS, 10mV amplitude from 1MHz to 10mHz with 12 points per decade (3 periods)
3. N x charge / rest 1 h / discharge / rest 1 h at a regime C.
4. Rest 4 hours

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5. PEIS, 10mV amplitude from 1MHz to 10mHz with 12 points per decade (3 periods)
6. Go to step 4 and switch to the next current regime

The cell reference capacity used for the calculation of the regimes is 5 mA.h.cm⁻² as this is what AM4BAT project aims at reaching. For each regime applied, the duration was set so that only the aimed capacity was exchanged. As such, the 5 mA.h.cm⁻² was used for calculating the intensity but only half this capacity was allowed to be exchanged. At each regime, between 5 and 10 cycles were performed to keep a reasonable testing time. Table 3 details the tests parameters associated to each regime. Cycling was allowed between 5V and -5V.

Table 3: Details related to the cycling protocol performed (cell reference capacity of 5 mA.h.cm⁻²).

Regimes	C	Current (mA.cm ⁻²)	Charge/Discharge duration (h)	Number of cycles N
C/20	0.05C	0.25	10	5
C/10	0.1C	0.5	5	10
C/3	0.33C	1.67	1.5	10
C	1C	5	0.5	10
2C	2C	10	0.25	10
3C	3C	15	0.17	10

1.2.4. Transference number evaluation using Bruce and Vincent protocol:

Bruce and Vincent protocol ¹ was selected for transference number measurements. It determines the current fraction due to lithium ions moving relatively to the total current through the cell. Tests were performed at 40°C and 25°C in Li/SE/Li coin-cell configuration with the following steps:

1. Rest 1 h
2. PEIS, 10mV amplitude from 1MHz to 10mHz with 8 points per decade (5 periods)
3. Rest 1 h
4. Chronoamperometry with +10mV imposed for 30 minutes
5. Rest 1 h
6. PEIS, 10mV amplitude from 1MHz to 10mHz with 8 points per decade (5 periods)

The transference number can be calculated using the formula $t_+ = \frac{I_{SS}(\Delta V - I_0 R_0)}{I_0(\Delta V - I_{SS} R_{SS})}$ where I_0 is the initial current during potential polarization in A, I_{SS} is the stationary current reached at the end of the potential polarization in A, ΔV is the polarization potential applied in V, and R_0 and R_{SS} are respectively the resistances before and after the potential polarization in Ω measured by EIS.

¹ Zugman et al, Electrochimica Acta 56 (2011) 3926-3933

1.2.5. OCV measurement protocol:

To determine OCV of the current collector, low regimes and GITT cycling tests are performed on half cells.

The low regimes use a C/50 current regime (0,1 mAh.cm²) which is calculated considering 5 mAh.cm² as the reference capacity.

The GITT experiments are done using C/50 pulses for 1 hour followed by 2 hour rests. The voltage measured at the end of the resting plotted as a function of the capacity exchanged during the C/50 pulses correspond to the OCV of the tested material.

1.2.6. EIS spectra interpretation:

The exploitation of the EIS spectra was performed by analysing Nyquist plots (normalized by the geometrical active surfaces) with the following electrical equivalent circuit: $R_0 + \frac{R_{SE}}{1+R_{SE}Q_{SE}(j\omega)^{\alpha_{SE}}} + \frac{R_{CT}}{1+R_{CT}Q_{CT}(j\omega)^{\alpha_{CT}}}$. With R_{SE} and R_{CT} respectively SE bulk and charge transfer resistances in $\Omega.cm^{-2}$, Q_{SE} and Q_{CT} respectively SE bulk and charge transfer associated capacitances in $F.cm^2$, and α_{SE} and α_{CT} respectively SE bulk and charge transfer associated offset coefficient.

Figure 5 presents the Nyquist plot associated with one of the EIS test performed and associate the different physical phenomena modelled by the selected electrical equivalent circuit to specific features observed on the spectra. Thus, the higher frequency loop is associated to the SE bulk resistance and the lower frequency loop is associated to the interfaces between the SE and either Li metal or the anode-less current collector.

Figure 5: Illustration of the different parts of the EIS spectra obtained with Li-SE-Li cells.

Once the EIS spectra are fitted with the selected equivalent electrical circuit, the SE bulk resistance R_{SE} and the charge transfer resistance R_{CT} can be used to calculate the SE conductivity and the exchange current density of the interfaces present in the cell.

The SE conductivity is obtained using $\sigma = \frac{L}{R_{SE}}$ where L is the SE thickness in cm , and R_{SE} is the SE bulk resistance in $\Omega.cm^{-2}$ calculated from fitting the higher frequencies of the EIS spectra.

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The exchange surface density is obtained using $I_0 = \frac{RT}{Z_{Li}FR_{CT}}$ where R is the gas constant in $kg.m^2.s^{-2}.K^{-1}.mol^{-1}$, T is the temperature in $^{\circ}K$, Z_{Li} is the charge number associated with lithium (= 1 for lithium), F is the Faraday constant in $A.s.mol^{-1}$, and R_{CT} is the charge transfer resistance in $\Omega.m^{-2}$ calculated from fitting the lower frequencies of the EIS spectra.

1.3. Results

First, the results associated with the characterization of batch 1 components is presented. For this batch 1, both the SE with 32% of LLZO and the SE with polymer only are tested. At this point of the project, the anode-less current collectors were not received, so only stainless steel and lithium symmetrical cells are assembled.

The cells with stainless steel were used for measuring the conductivity between 60°C and -10°C. The symmetrical cells with lithium metal are used to study the SE stability at 60°C.

Figure 6 presents the conductivity values for the SE with and without LLZO between 60°C and -10°C.

Figure 6: Conductivity measured for SE from batch 1 with and without LLZO.

The conductivity obtained for SE with LLZO is superior from the SE without LLZO. This observation is consistent with what was reported in modelling results from D6.1 which indicated a better conductivity of hybrid electrolytes but that predicted that the ceramic particle addition did not help increasing the lithium diffusion in the SE even if the ceramic /SE interface is perfect (Figure 7).

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Figure 7: ²Potentiostatic experiment simulation without ceramic particles (blue curve) and with particles for different transfer coefficient at the ceramic/spe interface: red curve $i_{0,cer/spe} = 0 \text{ A.m}^{-2}$, the yellow curve $i_{0,cer/spe} = 10 \text{ A.m}^{-2}$ and purple curve $i_{0,cer/spe} = 1000 \text{ A.m}^{-2}$.

Figure 8 compares the EIS obtained with lithium symmetrical cells every 2 hours at 60°C with the EIS from stainless steel symmetrical cells at 60°C.

For the lithium symmetrical cells, the impedance increases with increasing exposure time to the 60°C atmosphere. For the SE with LLZO, the interface resistance increases whereas the bulk resistance is constant. For the SE without LLZO, both the interface resistance and the bulk resistance increase.

Figure 8: Comparison of EIS spectra obtained at 60°C for different SE and cell designs.

The part of the EIS spectra associated with bulk resistance of lithium symmetrical cells are compared to the bulk resistance measured with the stainless steel symmetrical cells at the same temperature. It is clear that the bulk resistance is much higher when the SE are in contact with lithium metal. The evolution of the conductivity values are represented in Figure 9 and are compared with the values obtained in the stainless steel symmetrical configuration.

² Figure 4 from D6.1 deliverable of the AM4BAT project

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Figure 9: Comparison between the conductivity measured in Li/SE/Li and SS/SE/SS configuration for SE from batch 1 with and without LLZO.

The evolution of the interface between SE and lithium metal is represented in Figure 10 which draws the exchange current density values as a function of exposure time.

Figure 10: Evolution of the interface as a function of time for the 2 SE studied.

It was surprising to observe that the SE/Li interface is better when LLZO is present in the polymer matrix compared to the polymer only. Indeed, the main idea with hybrid electrolyte is to increase the SE conductivity by adding ceramic particles and while keeping a correct interface and flexibility with the polymer matrix.

For both SE studied, the interface improved at the beginning of exposure and then decreases due to the degradation of the interface.

Results from cycling stability tests at 60°C are presented in Figure 11. The cycling protocol performed is presented in section 1.2.3.

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Figure 11: Cycling tests and associated EIS at 60°C for SE from batch 1 with and without LLZO in Li/SE/Li configuration.

The cycling performed did not go as expected. Only very low capacities were exchanged at all regime tested due to very high polarization of the cells. Moreover, this polarization kept increasing as cycling was performed. This is visible with the evolution of the EIS spectra which illustrate this large resistance increase.

A maximum of 0,06 mAh was exchanged for the cell with 32% LLZO in the SE and a maximum of 0.16 mAh was exchanged for the cell without LLZO. The AM4BAT project aims at reaching a 5 mAh.cm² target which would correspond to a 7,7 mAh for the surface tested here.

Given the bad cyclability observed on the SE with and without LLZO, the presence of water in the SE was suspected. Fourier Transform InfraRed spectroscopy (FTIR) with Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR), was used on the SE from batch 1 to check possible LLZO contamination by H₂O traces. The raw results are presented Figure 12.

Figure 12: FTIR results related to the different SE from batch 1.

In presence of water traces, LLZO undergoes the reaction:

With the presence of CO₂, LiOH can further reacts: $2LiOH + CO_2 \rightarrow Li_2CO_3 + H_2O$

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This means that if LLZO reacted with water, Li_2CO_3 can be detected^{3 4}. This could explain why the exchange current density was better for the SE/Li interface when LLZO was present in the polymer matrix as observed in Figure 10. Indeed, the exchange current density calculation was biased but the reaction kinetics between LLZO and water.

The data from Figure 12 shows explicitly the presence of degradation product Li_2CO_3 in the spectra meaning that the SE tested are contaminated by water. The testing was stopped for these batch 1 materials until the new improved materials from batch 2 were provided by LEITAT.

EIS was performed on different cell configuration to investigate the SE bulk and the interfaces between the SE and lithium metal and/or anode-less current collector:

- SS/SE/SS to study the SE bulk only
- Li/SE/Li to study the SE bulk and the SE/Li interface
- Anode-less/SE/anode-less to study the SE bulk and the SE/ anode-less current collector interface
- Li/SE/anode-less to study the SE bulk and the SE/ anode-less current collector + SE/Li interfaces. This cell is in semi-blocking conditions because on one side the lithium can give and receive lithium ions, but on the other side the anode-less current collector can only receive lithium ion.

Figure 13 presents the EIS spectra obtained with the various configuration between 60°C and -10°C.

Figure 13: Raw impedance spectra from the SPE (batch 2) at different temperatures with various configurations.

³ Huo H, Luo J, Thangadurai V, Guo X, Nan CW, Sun X. Li_2CO_3 : A Critical Issue for Developing Solid Garnet Batteries. ACS Energy Lett. 2020;5(1):252-262.

⁴ Liu C, Rui K, Shen C, Badding ME, Zhang G, Wen Z. Reversible ion exchange and structural stability of garnet-type Nb-doped $Li_7La_3Zr_2O_{12}$ in water for applications in lithium batteries. J Power Sources. 2015;282:286-293.

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As expected, a clear dependency is observed as a function of temperatures for all tested configurations. The following Figure 14 compares the spectra at 20°C for the 4 tested configurations.

Figure 14: Comparison of impedance spectra from the SPE (batch 2) at 20°C with various configurations

The cells in blocking conditions (SS/SE/SS and Ag/SE/AG) represented in Figure 14 show similar behaviour in EIS. As expected, a semi-circle is visible at high temperatures which is representative of the SE bulk resistance. At lower temperatures, the EIS shape is quasi-vertical which is an effect of the capacitive behaviour of the cell due to the blocking conditions on both sides of the SE.

For the Li/SE/Li cell, the high frequency semi-circle is consistent with what is obtained in blocking conditions. At lower frequencies, a semi-circle starting by a linear shape is visible. This behaviour cannot be represented by the equivalent electrical circuit presented in section 1.2.6, hence it remains quite difficult to propose a physical explanation for this behaviour.

Finally for the Ag/SE/Li cell, which is in semi-blocking conditions, the high frequency semi-circle is similar to what was observed with the other configurations but a linear followed by capacitive shapes are observed at lower frequencies. The linear part of the spectrum follows a 45° angle, which could be representative of lithium diffusion, but evidences are still lacking to conclude on the matter.

Given the reproducible the behaviour obtained for the cells with different configurations, SE conductivity was calculated for each of them. Figure 15 represents the conductivity values obtained at the different temperatures which are also reported Table 4 in the case of the stainless steel symmetrical configuration for calculating the activation energy related to SE conductivity.

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Figure 15: Conductivity values obtained for SPE (batch 2) using various cell configurations.

The fact that the conductivities measured are independent from the cell configuration (Figure 15) is a sign that the SE studied is stable versus both lithium metal and the anode-less current collector. This was not the case for batch 1 SE where the conductivity values measured were much lower when lithium metal was present in the cell (Figure 9).

The results are presented in Table 4 for the SPE disks with 2.01cm² surface.

Table 4: EIS results: ionic conductivity of SPE as a function of temperature.

t, °C	Conductivity, μS/cm	
	Cell 1	Cell 2
20,3	11,41	8,79
61,5	71,74	55,48
41	35,01	26,13
20,3	14,31	10,60
-0,9	3,85	2,90
-11,6	1,66	1,27
-0,86	3,83	2,89
20,3	14,70	10,94
41,1	37,11	27,40
61,5	81,50	60,68
20,2	15,22	11,23
22,5	17,14	12,37

For the calculation of activation energies, conductivities as a function of temperature have been plotted in Arrhenius coordinates (Figure 16).

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Figure 16. EIS results for both tested cells in Arrhenius coordinates.

To calculate the activation Energy (E_a), a modified Arrhenius equation was used⁵:

$$\sigma T = A * \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right)$$

Linear fits of $\ln(\sigma T)$ vs $1/T$ correspond to $-E_a/R$, which brings us to activation energies of **39.9** and **39.8 kJ/mol** for cells 1 and 2 respectively.

Transference number was also evaluated for the SE studied. To do so Li/SE/Li cells were tested using the Bruce and Vincent protocol (see section 1.2.4).

Figure 17: Raw data from Bruce and Vincent tests performed at 25°C and 40°C.

Figure 17 presents the raw data from the Bruce and Vincent tests performed at 25°C and 40°C. This raw data was used in T6.1 for parametrizing and validating the model developed. The associated results are reported in D6.1.

The intensity values of interest are reported in Figure 17 and are associated to the resistances from Table 5 to calculate the transference number of the SE.

⁵ Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids 210 (2026) 113364

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Table 5: Resistances measured via EIS before and after potential polarization during the Bruce and Vincent tests.

	Resistance before polarization (Ω)	Resistance after polarization (Ω)
25°C	3213	3198
40°C	739	760

Interestingly, for both test at 25°C and 40°C the same value of 0,66 was calculated transference number. This value is lower than the aimed value of 0,9 (OB2 of the grant agreement).

Thermal stability tests were performed at 60°C for Li/SE/Li configuration and the results are reported in Figure 18. The stability of the SE from batch 2 is slightly better than for SE from batch 1 (Figure 10) but it still evolves with exposure time. Here the test was performed at 60°C to accelerate the degradation and this selected temperature was probably too high. It would have been interesting to test other temperatures but it was not possible due to the limited SE resources allocated to T6.3.

Figure 18: EIS results from stability tests at 60°C on Li/SE/Li from batch 2.

Cycling stability tests were also performed at 25°C to be coherent with the aims of this project. The cells manufactured did not work and it was not possible to assemble other cells.

Anode-less current collectors with Ag coated were tested in the previously reported activities. However, LEITAT provided another anode-less current collectors with a Sn coating. This Sn coated current collector was not tested regarding SE stability.

To provide data for T6.2 modelling activities performed by VUB, the OCV of both the Ag and Sn coated current collectors were characterized.

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To do so, half coin cells were assembled. A liquid electrolyte (LPX + 2%VC) was used as here the aim is to obtain the current collectors' OCV which is not dependent on the type of electrolyte associated to it.

After cell assembly, the lithiation of the current collectors were done with both the low regime (C/50) and the GITT protocols detailed in section 1.2.5.

Figure 19: GITT and C/50 data for the lithiation of Ag and Sn current collectors.

Figure 19 presents the data obtained for both Ag and Sn coated current collectors. A large polarization between the OCV and low regime data (around 100mV) which is representative of the high interface resistance between the current collectors and the electrolyte. From the obtained curves, lithium deposition is possible only once the cell voltage goes below 0V. Above 0V, insertion of lithium happens in the current resulting in the formation of an alloy.

For the Sn coated current collector, at low regime (C/50), lithium deposition is observed only after 6,12 mA.h.cm⁻² are exchanged. For the GITT test, the capacity until lithium deposition starts is above 7 mA.h.cm⁻².

For the Ag coated current collector, at low regime (C/50), lithium deposition is observed only after 0,56 mA.h.cm⁻² are exchanged. For the GITT test, the capacity until lithium deposition starts is above 9 mA.h.cm⁻².

A clear difference in OCV shape is observed between the two coatings. For the Sn coating, a large part of the OCV is above 300 mV, whereas for the Ag coating the quasi-totality of the OCV is below 75mV. In dynamic conditions the plating onset will be dependent from the current applied.

This indicates that a much larger current is necessary to plate lithium on the Sn coating than for the Ag coating. As such, the Ag coating is more suitable to be used as a lithium deposition substrate.

The reversibility of the alloying and deposition processes happening on both coating was investigated in Figure 20. A large irreversibility is observed which could be a sign that all the plated lithium could not be extracted from the current collectors.

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Figure 20: GITT and C/50 data for the lithiation and delithiation of Ag and Sn current collectors.

1.4. SAXS/WAXS characterization of the HSE film

Small and wide angle X ray scattering (SAXS/WAXS) analyses were performed in a Xenocs Xeuss 3.0 to study the temperature dependent structural properties of the HSE film from batch 2, see Figure 21. The sample was mounted on a heating stage and three different temperatures were applied as verified by means of an attached thermocouple: 25°C, 45°C and 60°C. The measurements were performed in vacuum conditions (pressure < 1 mbar). It was previously verified that the polymer is stable under those conditions using Kapton tape to protect the polymer.

Figure 21 : Experimental setup in the SAXS device for measurements up to 60°C.

Figure 22 shows the SAXS intensity distribution. Analyses were performed at a sample to detector distance of 1.8 m and the scattering intensity, which was found to be perfectly isotropic, was radially integrated. The polymer structure at this Q-vector range, which translates in real space coordinates to approximately 6 nm - 160 nm, is unchanged when modifying the temperature, which shows the stability of the structural properties. The signal is quite amorphous with some low ordering. Applying correlation function analysis to the signal a long period L_p of the polymer could be calculated as 63 nm. This long period ordering is the sum of an amorphous block L_a of 59 nm and a crystalline block L_c of 4 nm, see insert in Figure 22.

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Figure 22 : (left) SAXS intensity signal (2D) at room temperature of the polymer showing isotropic behaviour and (right) Radial integration of the intensity to reduce data from 2D to 1D as a function of temperature.

Figure 23 shows the WAXS intensity distribution. Again, an amorphous behaviour is found when radially integrating the WAXS intensity because clear crystalline peaks, which are observable for semi-crystalline polymers in literature are missing. The structure at this Q range, which translates to the range of 0.3 nm - 0.9 nm in real space coordinates, shows in analogy to the SAXS structural analysis only disturbed crystalline elements. The signal remains too amorphous to evaluate lattice parameters and more. The signal didn't change again as a function of temperature.

Figure 23 : (left) WAXS intensity signal (2D) at room temperature of the polymer showing isotropic behaviour for the observed angular range and (right) Radial integration of the intensity to reduce data from 2D to 1D.

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Thus, SAXS/WAXS analyses confirm that the HSE film maintains stable structural properties across the investigated temperature range (25–60 °C). The SAXS data reveal an essentially isotropic and largely amorphous morphology with only weak long-range ordering, characterized by a long period of approximately 63 nm consisting predominantly of an amorphous phase. WAXS measurements further support this finding, showing no distinct crystalline peaks and indicating only disturbed crystalline domains. Overall, the polymer structure remains unchanged with temperature, demonstrating the thermal stability of the material within the studied conditions.

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2. Post-mortem study

A key part of this project was to investigate ways to perform post-mortem analyses on solid state batteries (SSB). The main difference with Gen3 batteries is that the stack cannot be separated for SSB as presented Figure 24.

Figure 24: Picture of coin-cell stack after disassembling.

Cryo-fracture was the selected technique for these post-mortem studies to analyse cross-sections. After opening the coin-cell in the glove-box, the stack is transferred to the dry room. Liquid nitrogen is poured in an insulated recipient and then the SSB stack is plunged in it for a minute. After removing the SSB stack, a sharp scalpel is used to cut it in half, hence creating the cross-section that will be observed using SEM.

2.1. Results

Cryo-fracture was first performed for batch 1 as shown in Figure 25.

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(a)

(b)

Figure 25: SEM observation of stack cross-section for (a) Li/SPE/Li and (b) Li/HSPE/Li from batch 1.

Figure 25 (a) presents the results for a lithium vs lithium cell with a SE containing no LLZO. Very mossy lithium electrodes can be observed, with the presence of dendrites at the lithium/SE interfaces. The SE/lithium interfaces are also not perfect with loss of contact visible in some places. Measuring the thicknesses of the different cell components was challenging due to the lack of contrast between the different layers. The cryo-fracture process was also not perfect and affected the interfaces that were studied.

In Figure 25 (b), a lithium vs lithium cell with a SE containing 32_w% of LLZO is represented. Again, the SE/lithium interfaces are difficult to identify. The LLZO dispersion in the polymer matrix is not homogeneous.

Cycled cells from batch 2 have also been investigated post-mortem with the cryo-fracture technique. For this batch 2, Li vs Ag anode-less current collector and Li vs Li cells containing SE without LLZO were looked at (Figure 26).

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Figure 26: SEM observation of stack cross-section for (a) Al vs Li and (b) Li vs Li configurations using SPE from batch 2.

On Figure 26 (a), the different parts of the Ag/SE/Li stack can be observed. A very neat cross section was obtained and the different layers were observed. The layers did not stick together. The SE size is observed to be round 315 μm on the cross sections compared to around 400 μm measured during cell assembly. This difference can be explained by the pressure applied in the coin-cell. Also, if the cross-section observed is not perfectly horizontal, then a slight measurement bias can arise from this tilt. The Ag and Li electrodes were identified. No particular features were observed on their interfaces, as the cell was not able to cycle a lot before this post-mortem observation. A 45 μm thick lithium electrode (vs 50 μm expected) and a 15 μm anode-less current collector were measured (vs 20-25 μm expected) which are coherent with the expected values measured during cell assembly.

Figure 26 (b) presents a Li/SE/Li stack with also a clean cross section. For this stack, some parts stayed stuck together after cryo-fracture and some did not. The lithium electrodes have a thickness measured around 50 μm , which is similar to what was measured during assembly. The SE is measured at 320 μm . No particular features were observed on their interfaces, as the cell was not able to cycle a lot before this post-mortem observation.

One Ag/SE/Li stack was also sectioned using an ionic cutting equipment. Only one trial could be made due to a later equipment failure. Optical images of the cross-section are presented in Figure 27. The different parts of the stack did not stick together during the ionic cutting. A SE thickness of 300 μm was measured. The cut quality made it difficult to study the Ag and Li electrodes. An adaptation of the ionic cut process should be performed to better observed

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cross-sections of SSB. This technique remains interesting because it can potentially create cleaner section than cryo-fracture.

Figure 27: Optical microscope observation of a Ag/SE/Li stack cross-section obtained with ionic cutting.

3. Conclusions

The task 6.3 of the AM4BAT project allowed the characterization of the solid electrolytes developed in the project as well as the SE/lithium metal and SE/anode-less current collectors interfaces.

Thermal stability tests were performed at 60°C, which was probably too high for the purpose of the project but they showed some instabilities between the solid electrolytes developed and lithium metal. Cycling the cells was very difficult and only low capacities were exchanged which affect the safety evaluation regarding dendrite growth.

Nevertheless, some data generated in task 6.3 provided input parameters for task 6.1 and 6.2.

SAXS/WAXS analyses performed on the hybrid solid electrolyte confirms that the polymer structure remains unchanged with temperature, demonstrating the thermal stability of the material within the studied conditions.

For post-mortem activities, the best solution is to observe cross-sections of the cell stack obtained via cryo-fracture. An ionic cutting process was also considered but more developments are needed to give clean cross-sections.